

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES OF MEMORIZING NEW WORDS OF THE
KOREAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *The article discusses different ways of memorizing new words and analyzes the methods used by Korean language learners.*

Key words: *vocabulary, word memorization, word memorization methods, cognitive methods, metacognitive methods, mnemonics, perception channel, auditory learners, visual learners, kinesthetic learners, systematic memorization, involuntary learning, practical exercise.*

The study of a foreign language is divided into the areas of speaking, listening, reading, and writing, and the assessment of the level of mastery of these four criteria plays an important role in determining the ability to know a foreign language. However, lexical skills, which are a key element of any language, should not be overlooked. Vocabulary is one of the key factors in a student's success in language learning. As a basis for mastering reading, listening, writing and speaking, a lot of research is being carried out to identify the most widely used and effective vocabulary memorization methods today.

A well-known Korean linguist Yim Ji-a said, "Vocabulary selection includes the subjective selection method and the objective selection method. Subjective choice is the study of words as they are translated, and objective selection is the study of words in a given context. In both cases, the student's vocabulary gradually increases. Therefore, the criteria and methods for selecting and presenting the vocabulary being studied are very important to maximize the student's ability to learn vocabulary" [1].

According to Schmit the methods of word memorization are divided into two groups: discovery (methods of determining the meaning of a word) and consolidation (methods of memorizing a word after studying it). He includes in Group 1 methods such as using dictionaries, studying the meaning of a word according to its meaning in the text, and asking a teacher or group member about the meaning of a word. Group 2 is divided into cognitive, metacognitive and memory methods:

- cognitive strategies – written and spoken repetition, writing words on flash cards, making word lists, keeping a vocabulary notebook, taking notes during the lesson;
- metacognitive strategies – these methods are used by students to control and evaluate their own learning, by having an overview of the learning process in general. They include ways to organize the learning process, select teaching materials, take tests and exercises, and review what they have learned;

- memory strategies – forming meaningful words and phrases from the capital letters of the information to be memorized (acronyms), creating an image related to the word itself or its meaning, memorizing the words by associating them with another word, an event, action, state, tone, object, person (association), memorizing words according to their location (notebook or book page, board, etc.) [2]. This set of special methods for remembering information based on similarities and connections is also called mnemonics.

Most language learners take the process of memorizing words as an obligation, and as a result, memorizing words becomes a difficult and tedious activity for them. The main reason for this is that the methods of word memorization in language learning are not advanced and convenient. To cope with the difficulty in learning vocabulary experienced linguists, polyglots (multilingual speakers) and teachers offer the following suggestions:

1. Determine the type of your perception channel (auditory, visual, kinesthetic) [3]. Visual learners are better able to retain information by seeing or observing things such as charts, diagrams, pictures, demonstrations, displays, handouts, films, flip-charts. Auditory learners learn best through their sense of hearing. This means they remember and understand new concepts better when they are explained out loud – even if they are doing the speaking themselves. Kinesthetic learners absorb information best through physical experience – touching, feeling, holding, doing, practical hands-on experiences. Once the language learner has determined his type of perception channel, the learner can effectively organize the process of word memorization using interactive methods that are convenient for him.

2. Apart from what has been mentioned above, it should be kept in mind that knowing the translation of a word is not always enough to fully master the information: "Knowing a word does not mean memorizing its translation or interpretation. Even if a student knows the translation and definition of a word, it still does not mean anything, because the problem that many teachers face is that the student knows the meaning of the word but cannot understand the essence of the sentence "[4]. Therefore, it is important that the learner not only remembers the word, but also understands and uses it correctly when needed. Korean linguist Kim Kwang-hee also calls the student's vocabulary "the breadth of knowledge". He describes the ability to use the words he knows in their place as "depth of understanding" [5]. Vocabulary is not just about knowing many words, but also about understanding the meaning of each word and its relationship to other words. Therefore, Kim Kwang-Hee emphasizes that a qualitative and effective method of improving lexical skills in Korean is to study the relationship of each word with other words and to find the meaning or antonyms of each word. Only then will he have a real lexical skill.

3. There are two types of word learning: involuntary learning of new words and conscious learning of words. Experts say that involuntary learning of new words helps to learn information faster and more efficiently than systematically organized learning. For example, a person driving a car may be on the road with all his attention, but his mind will involuntarily accept the words of a song heard from a car tape recorder. Kato Lomb, one of the world's first simultaneous translators, recommends in his well known book "How do I learn a language?" that watching more movies and videos, listening to the radio, reading a

variety of literature and newspapers, and interacting with people who speak the language contribute significantly to their language learning, particularly vocabulary learning [6]. In this case, the mind is focused on the plot and involuntarily learns new words and phrases.

A small survey was conducted in the form of a questionnaire to examine what methods students use to memorize words and how effective they are in learning Korean. The survey is based on Schmit's word memorization methods. In this small-scale study, twenty students who were studying the Korean language at Uzbekistan World Languages University were selected to participate. Initially, the students were divided into two groups: those who learned words easily and those who had difficulty memorizing words. The following table lists the most commonly used methods by students in both groups.

Students who learn words easily Students who have difficulty memorizing words

Students who learn words easily		Students who have difficulty memorizing words	
№	Most used methods	№	Most used methods
1.	<i>Memorizing words in the form of combinations, phrases, sentences</i>	1.	<i>Spoken repetition</i>
2.	<i>Making sentences with learned words</i>	2.	<i>Written repetition</i>
3.	<i>Pair work (questions and answers), quizzes</i>	3.	<i>Pair work (questions and answers), quizzes</i>
4.	<i>Finding synonyms and antonyms for word</i>	4.	<i>Reviewing new words by reading (test papers, books, news)</i>
5.	<i>Watching movies, cartoons, videos, TV programs and listening to songs in Korean</i>	5.	<i>Watching movies, cartoons, videos, TV programs and listening to songs in Korean</i>
6.	<i>Using the association method</i>	6.	<i>Using the association method</i>
7.	<i>Written repetition</i>	7.	<i>Creating an image of the word</i>
8.	<i>Spoken repetition</i>	8.	<i>Finding synonyms and antonyms for words</i>
9.	<i>Reviewing new words by reading (test papers, books, news)</i>	9.	<i>Memorizing words in the form of combinations, phrases, sentences</i>
10.	<i>Creating an image of the word</i>		
11.	<i>Reviewing vocabulary at regular intervals,</i>		

An analysis of the survey results showed that Group 1 students used more methods of word memorization than Group 2 students. Written and spoken repetition, watching Korean movies, cartoons, videos, listening to songs, using the association method, learning words in the text while reading are the methods used by both groups of students. The difference in successful word acquisition is reflected in the use of practical exercises. Group

1 students use the new words and combinations they have learned in a sentence, compose texts and stories, and reinforce words through tests. Group 2 students, on the other hand, do not use words in practice, focusing on only the meaning of the word and its memorization. At the same time, students also mentioned methods such as using an a definition dictionary, memorizing words by adapting the meaning and pronunciation of some Korean words to Uzbek, writing words on flash cards, memorizing base words and so on.

In short, the most commonly used and effective methods in the process of learning the Korean language are written and spoken repetition of words, learning new words in the form of compounds and expressions, watching movies, cartoons, videos in Korean, listening to songs, composing sentences, stories and texts from learned words, applying them in practice and repeating words at regular intervals. This result is only relevant to the group which was surveyed. In fact, there is no one-size-fits-all method of memorizing words, and the student's ability to identify and use the methods that are convenient for him or her is the basis for perfect language learning. In the future, as a follow-up to this small study, researches on how to make Korean language lessons fun with word-learning activities will be useful.

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